

Strategic Groundwater Management Using Aquifer Mapping: A Gram Panchayat Level Study in Tumkur district, Karnataka

Suchetana Biswas*

Central Ground Water Board, South Western Region, HSR Layout, Sector-1, Bengaluru-560102, Karnataka, India

ABSTRACT

Groundwater sustainability and management are crucial for regions experiencing resource depletion. This study focuses on aquifer mapping and strategic groundwater management at the Gram Panchayat level in Bukkapatna, Koratagere Taluk, Tumkur District, Karnataka, India. The study aims to develop a comprehensive groundwater management plan that ensures sustainable and equitable resource utilization, particularly in an area with an agriculture-driven economy and a semi-arid climate characterized by low rainfall and seasonal water scarcity. Field investigations were conducted to assess hydrogeological parameters, including rock formations, aquifer characteristics, groundwater levels, water quality, and irrigation practices. The study identifies two primary aquifer systems—an unconfined phreatic aquifer and a semi-confined fractured aquifer. Data analysis led to the creation of aquifer disposition and groundwater quality maps, enabling the development of targeted management plans. The study highlights significant issues such as declining groundwater levels, inefficient irrigation practices, and inadequate recharge structures. Management recommendations include supply-side measures like desilting tanks, constructing recharge structures, and implementing rainwater harvesting, alongside demand-side measures such as reviving traditional water bodies "Talapariges", promoting micro-irrigation, reducing water wastage, and fostering community participation in groundwater governance. Results indicate that while groundwater quality is generally suitable for consumption, localized contamination issues exist due to agricultural runoff. To enhance groundwater sustainability, the study advocates for a participatory groundwater management approach, integrating scientific data with community-based interventions. The proposed framework provides a replicable model for sustainable groundwater governance at the village level, ensuring long-term water security and resilience in semi-arid regions.

Keywords: Groundwater Management, Aquifer Mapping, Water Scarcity, Sustainable Irrigation, Participatory Governance

INTRODUCTION

Groundwater serves as a crucial resource, particularly in regions where surface water is either scarce, non-perennial, or polluted[1]. In such contexts, it acts as a lifeline for drinking water supply, agriculture, and overall socio-economic development. In semi-arid areas like Karnataka, India, groundwater becomes even more vital, given the erratic rainfall patterns and dependency on subsistence agriculture[2]. However, the over-extraction and mismanagement of groundwater resources have led to declining water tables, quality degradation, and increased vulnerability to water scarcity. While large-scale regional aquifer mapping provides a broad

understanding of groundwater systems[3,4], village-level mapping and management are critical in addressing the unique challenges of Karnataka's diverse and localized hydrogeological conditions.

Regional studies often generalize these variations, making them inadequate for developing site-specific solutions. Village-level mapping allows for a micro-scale understanding of aquifer behavior, enabling tailored interventions based on local conditions.

To address these challenges, the concept of micro-level aquifer mapping and management at village level has emerged as a comprehensive approach to ensure sustainable groundwater use. This paper focuses on aquifer management strategies developed

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

for Bukkapatna Gram Panchayat, located in Koratagere Taluk, Tumkur district, Karnataka.

Objective and Methodology of the study

The primary objective of the study is to ensure sustainable and equitable utilization of groundwater resources while addressing the challenges of water scarcity and drought resilience. This involves securing a reliable drinking water supply, enhancing irrigation facilities for agriculture, and identifying vulnerable areas with declining water levels or poor-quality water for targeted interventions. The study aims to promote groundwater recharge through site-specific measures, such as recharge wells and check dams, while encouraging efficient water use practices. By fostering community participation and awareness, the initiative seeks to empower local stakeholders to manage groundwater resources responsibly. Additionally, it supports policy implementation by providing granular data and actionable insights to inform sustainable water resource management, ensuring long-term water security and resilience in this semi-arid region.

Various information on ground water occurrence in borewells, depth of casing, occurrence of fractures

and yield reported, water samples were collected through field study and analysed. The thematic maps of depth to water level, weathered zone, hydrogeology and artificial recharge points are prepared Arc-GIS software. Both supply and demand side groundwater management plan for study area has been prepared in accordance with the nature of the aquifer, its quality of water, and stress on the resource. The management plans can be implemented by the stakeholders/user agencies as per conditions.

Study area

Bukkapatna gram panchayat comes under Koratagere taluk, Tumkur district of Karnataka, India. It comprises of 08 villages namely: Bukkapatna, Baraka, Gatlagolahalli, Gatlahalli, Hirejenahalli, Venkanahalli, Veerobanahalli, and Gondihalli. The spatial extent of the gram Panchayat is between 13.49° N to 13.54° N latitude and 77.150° E to 77.220° E longitude.

It comes under Survey of India Topo-sheet No. 57 G/2(1:50,000 scale). The total area of the Gram Panchayat is 28.90Sq.Km.The total population of the village is 6693 persons (Census 2011)[5].

The location map of the study area is given in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Location map of Bukkapatna gram panchayat

Physiographically, the area is a part of the Southern Karnataka plateau. A number of rocky hillocks and boulders are also dispersed throughout the Panchayat. Piedmont zones are another important feature with weathered formations having maximum thickness of 30 m (Figure 2).The Panchayat is located in the

watershed of Suvarnamukhi river. The area is drained by ephemeral streams that flow only during the monsoon season and dry up during summer. The general drainage pattern is sub-rectangular. (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Drainage and geomorphology map of Bukkapatna gram panchayat

The area experiences a semi-arid type of climate characterized by hot summer and low rainfall. Agro-climatically it falls in the central dry zone of Karnataka State. The region experiences an average minimum temperature of 17.3°C and an average maximum temperature of 35°C. The normal annual rainfall of Koratagere taluk is 760mm, and most of the rainfall is experienced during the South-West monsoon. The predominant soils are red soils also known as Ragi soil. They are derived from the acidic type of rocks like granite and gneisses and occupy the entire panchayat. The gram panchayat has a total geographical area of 2890.6 hectares. Forest cover is limited to 311.4 hectares. Agriculture and cultivation are the predominant land use of the area. Total irrigated land area is 278.7 ha i.e.10 % of the total area. Cultivable wasteland is 5.8 ha i.e.0.2 % of the total area. Net sown area is 1588.2 hectares. Unirrigated area is 1309.5 ha i.e. 45% Of total area and 82.5% of net sown area. Uncultivable waste land is 11.48 % of the total area[6]. Since, there is no irrigation by canals, the major mode of irrigation is rainfed irrigation and by means of pumping from deep bore wells fitted with submersible electric motors. Kharif period is the main cropping season. Major food crops are Ragi, Maize, Paddy. The major oil seeds grown groundnut. Coconut, areca nut, mulberry, banana, tomato, papaya are some of the plantation and horticultural crops cultivated in the area. Out of the

total geographical area of 2890.6 ha, the net sown area is 1588.2ha. The area irrigated by wells/borewells is 249.9ha and area irrigated by tanks/lakes is 28.8ha. The total irrigated area is 278.7 ha and total unirrigated area is 1309.5ha[6]. The area is underlain predominantly by granite gneisses. Massive exposures of granite gneisses are seen in the Western, South-Western and Northern portion of the panchayat. The average depth to weathered zone is 20m.

HYDROGEOLOGY

Types of Aquifers:

- i. Aquifer-I (Phreatic/Unconfined aquifer) comprising of weathered granite gneiss
- ii. Aquifer-II (Semi-confined/Fractured aquifer system) comprising of fractured granite gneiss.

In the study area, the depth of weathered zone varies between 10.67 mbgl to 36.5m bgl (Figure 3). Phreatic aquifer is confined within this depth range. The total depth of the bore-wells varies between 137.16mbgl to 274.32mbgl. Most of the borewells have only one water yielding fracture zone. The fracture zones reported by the village watermen/farmers vary between 70m bgl to 244 m bgl. (Figure 4,5,6). The average discharge reported in the area is about 1.0-1.5 lps. Post-monsoon water level varies from 32.60m bgl to 52.77m bgl. The wells are used for drinking water purpose and irrigation.

Figure 3: Depth to weathered zone map of Bukkapatna gram panchayat

Figure 4: 3D aquifer model of Bukkapatna gram panchayat

Figure 5: Location map of studied wells

Figure 6: Strip logs of the studied wells

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Quality of Water

Table 1: Results of chemical analysis of water samples

Sl.No	Location	PH	EC	TH	Ca	Mg	Na	K	CO3	HCO3	Cl	SO4	NO3	F
			μS/cm	<.....mg/L.....>										
1	Bukkapatna	6.957	833	242	78.4	11	74	3	0	305	85	45	24	1.35
2	Baraka	7.010	978	322	92.4	22	83	2.6	0	366	128	66	7	0.75
3	Gatlagollahalli	7.208	1503	529.5	194	11	99	3.8	0	458	163	114	100	0.95
4	Gatlahalli	7.111	1049	333	102	19	83	3.5	0	415	135	59	6	0.96
5	Venkanahalli	7.052	576	173	46.2	14	55	2.1	0	287	36	28	0	0.87
6	Hirejanahalli	7.141	626	184.5	55.4	11	66	1.5	0	366	36	15	2	1.14
7	Veerobanahalli	7.171	906	230	69.2	14	95	2.4	0	372	71	54	32	1.25
8	Gondihalli	7.151	783	218.5	59.8	17	81	2.7	0	329	50	48	21	0.97
9	Gondihalli Plantation	7.160	508	138	35.8	12	53	3	0	207	43	8	37	1.48

In Bukkapatna gram panchayat, groundwater samples were collected from 9 borewells representing Aquifer –II (fractured semi-confined aquifer). Interpretation from Chemical Analysis result is mentioned as under table 1:

The values of pH, EC, cations and anions are within the permissible limit mentioned in Bureau of Indian Standards BIS (IS_10500 and revised module IS 10500:2012) for drinking water. Nitrate (found to exceed the permissible limit of 45mg/L) in one Gatlagollahalli village (100 mg/L) only. Groundwater quality, in general, is good and potable. It is suitable for domestic and irrigation purposes.

Since the borewell from which sample was collected in Gatlagollahalli village is located close to agricultural field, Nitrate contamination is occurring in the aquifer due to some point source like agricultural runoff, indicating anthropogenic origin.

Piper diagram (Figure 7) plotted for the samples indicates the following:

- a) In terms of cations, the water samples show no dominant type
- b) In terms of anions, the water samples are dominantly bicarbonate type
- c) Overall, the ternary diagram indicates that the groundwater of the study area is dominantly of Calcium-Magnesium-Bicarbonate type.

Figure 7: Piper diagram of water samples collected from Bukkapatna gram panchayat

STATUS OF GROUNDWATER USE

Irrigation sector

There are two agricultural seasons, namely Kharif (June – October) and Rabi season (Mid October – Mid February), apart from summer crops. The extraction of ground water for irrigation is 292.6ham.

During field study, it was observed that, most farmers in this gram panchayat had not adopted micro-irrigation practices yet. They were extensively following the normal flood irrigation. Erratic and deficient rainfall in preceding years and traditional farming practices leads to severe water crisis during Rabi season.

Domestic Consumption

The Gram panchayat has a population of 6693 persons with 1555 households. The livestock population is about 8000 consist of cows/ buffaloes, sheep, goat, poultry. The annual domestic demand is 14.21ham. Around 450 households have been provided with piped water supply connections. There are 4 Over Head Tanks of 50,000cc to 1,00,000cc in 3 villages and 61 cisterns and 58 public taps in the gram panchayat. There are 13 deep bore wells with average pumping duration at 6 hrs/day.

MANAGEMENT PLAN

The gram panchayat being agriculture-based economy, groundwater is mostly utilized for irrigation. Since it is in over-exploited category, it requires strict regulation in use. In order to maintain sustainability of this resource, both supply side and

demand side management practices need to be followed.

Demand and Supply-side Issues

The issues plaguing the study area are as follows:

- Drying up of source of domestic water supply & irrigation wells due to over extraction of resource, erratic rainfall, nature of terrain and improper disposal of garbage.
- Drying up of tanks due to silt accumulation which reduces storage capacity
- Lack of proper maintenance recharge structures
- Point source of contamination of groundwater
- Wastage of water due to leakage/absence of taps in standpost, leakage in water supply channels and not switching off pumps even after cistern gets filled.

Supply-side Management measures

- Desiltation of tanks/Renovation of tanks: Bukkapatna gram panchayat has 5 big lakes. They are mostly ephemeral and have little water during summer. The lead channels and foreclosure to the tanks are filled/ utilised for other purposes. Hence inflow is reduced. Besides, the tanks also get silted up in due course of time leading to reduced storage reservoir. Removing the silt will improve storage capacity and groundwater recharge [7].
- Augmentation of the resources: Suitable artificial recharge structures like checkdams, farm ponds with recharge pits, recharge wells are to be constructed in the gram panchayat (Figure 8,9) [8]. Since this gram panchayat is located in the foothills, sufficient scope exists to harvest the surface runoff after rainfall. Periodical

maintenance of artificial recharge structures should be implemented. The abandoned dug wells

and bore wells may be converted into recharge wells.

Figure 8: Farm pond being constructed in study area

Figure 9: Cattle pond (go- katte) in the study area for rain water harvesting and groundwater recharge as well as drinking water for cattle

- Construction/Maintenance of Rainwater Harvesting structures like farm ponds, step wells, tanks and roof top rain water harvesting structure for government building.
- Proper operation and maintenance of water supply structures and systems is required. All leakages/ other faults should be rectified at the earliest to avoid loss and wastage of water. Proper training is to be imparted to village watermen.
- Interaction programmes to sensitise people about the importance of this dwindling resource and involving them in water conservation programmes.

Demand side management measures suggested:

Apart from recharge of groundwater, steps need to be taken to decrease the volume of water consumed.

- Since the study area is surrounded by hillocks, there are several “Talapariges” (point where the underground water oozes or springs out) seen during field work. The farmers have made small dugwells of 1m*1m*1.5/2m dimension in the field which automatically gets filled with groundwater after monsoon (Figure 10)[9][10]. The water is used for domestic purposes like washing, cleaning and bathing as also for ragi, vegetables and fodder grass cultivation. Such practices are to be encouraged and taken up more intensely.

Figure 10: Talaparige water being collected and used for agriculture and domestic purposes in Bukkapatna Gram Panchayat

- Participatory groundwater management approach is to be encouraged among the people who are the owners of bore wells to develop a sense of responsibility towards the resource. Village level ground water user group to be formed to discuss the water budget for every year[11].
- Micro-irrigation practices like drip and sprinkler irrigation and plastic mulching methods need to be adopted. Farmers need to be encouraged and sensitized by the concerned line departments.
- Rain gauge stations and Water level monitoring stations: Regular monitoring of water level to be overlooked by panchayat authorities responsible for maintenance of water needs of the panchayat.

CONCLUSIONS

In the study area, scarcity of groundwater is the key issue. An effort has been made to prepare “Village Level Ground Water Management Plan” by analysing the information on groundwater and the factors influencing its occurrence, collected through field study. The demand and supply side management plans have been prepared and suitable remedies have been discussed based on the issues faced in the gram panchayat. Community awareness and participation is important in the management efforts. Augmentation of the resources by artificial recharge measures, desiltation of tanks/renovation of tanks, construction/maintenance of rainwater harvesting structures, water tanks, wells, and training to operators, farmers, and domestic consumers in optimal use of water are suggested. Forming water user group at village level, taking up micro irrigation practices, reviving local water structures like “Talapariges”, rainfall and water level monitoring are some of the ways to manage the resource efficiently in the long run.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The author is grateful to the Chairman, Central Ground Water Board and the Regional Director, South Western Region, Central Ground Water Board for giving the opportunity to publish this paper. The author is grateful to the Gram Panchayat officials and villagers of Bukkapatna for the help rendered during data collection

REFERENCE

1. Priyan, Khadeeja. (2021). Issues and Challenges of Groundwater and Surface Water Management in Semi-Arid Regions. 10.1007/978-3-030-68124-1_1.
2. CGWB, Groundwater Information Booklet, Tumkur District, Karnataka, 2008
3. Jha, B.M. & Sinha, S.K. 2009 Towards Better Management of Ground Water Resources in India. Bhujal News, Vol.No.24, No.4, October-December 2009, 1-20
4. Kinzelbach, W., Bauer, P., Siegfried, T. & Brunner, P. 2003 Sustainable groundwater management —problems and scientific tools. Institute for Hydromechanics and Water Resources Management, ETH Zürich, Switzerland. Episodes, Vol. 26, no. 4, 279-284
5. Tumkur District Census Handbook 2011 Directorate of Census Operations Karnataka
6. Tumkur District at A Glance, 2016-17, Govt. of Karnataka
7. Manjunatha M.C., Ahmed A. & Basavarajappa H.T. 2020 Artificial Recharge Structures for Groundwater Augmentation in Mysuru Taluk of Karnataka State, India using Geospatial Technology. JECET; September 2020-November 2020; Sec. A; Vol.9. No.4, 652-674.
8. Master Plan for Artificial Recharge to Groundwater in India (2020) – A CGWB Compilation
9. Mudakavi, D. 2021 Water heritage in the age of scarcity. Deccan Herald-Spectrum
10. Puttaramaiah, G., Panduranga Murthy, G & Mallikarjun H. Evaluation of Drinking water quality in some ‘Talapariges’ of Tumkur District, Karnataka, India. Invited Lecture, Section: Environmental Sciences at 102nd Indian Science Congress, University of Mumbai, Mumbai
11. Reddy, V.R., Reddy, M.S. & Rout, S.K. 2014. Groundwater governance: A tale of three participatory models in Andhra Pradesh, India. *Water Alternatives* 7(2): 275-297

HOW TO CITE: Suchetana Biswas, Strategic Groundwater Management Using Aquifer Mapping: A Gram Panchayat Level Study in Tumkur district, Karnataka, *Int. J. Sci. R. Tech.*, 2025, 2 (2), 25-32. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14824471>